

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MATRIX CHARACTERISTICS
AND COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

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EXPERIMENTS and RESULTS

1. Specimens have been prepared with two types of resin systems: Epoxy-648 (highly crosslinked) and Epoxy-634 (moderate crosslinked). The mechanical properties of these resins have been tested, including tensile moduli, ultimate strains and strengths along with compressive moduli and strengths. The testing results are summarized in table 1.

It is shown in table 1 that the tensile modulus of Epoxy-634 was slightly less than Epoxy-648's, but its tensile strength was as twice as Epoxy-648's. The ultimate tensile strains were 2.66% for Epoxy-634 and 1.24% for Epoxy-648, which resulted from different chemical constructions. It was observed from the experiments that the compressive strength of Epoxy-648 was slightly higher than Epoxy-634's.

2. Unidirectional and $\pm 45^\circ$ composites have been prepared using T300 carbon fibers and above resins. The longitudinal and transverse tensile, longitudinal compressive and shear in plane and interlaminar shear properties have been tested. The results are shown in table 2.

(1). The longitudinal tensile moduli of the unidirectional composites depend mainly on the properties and volumes of the fibers. However, longitudinal tensile strengths depend not only on the fiber properties but also on the fracture models and matrix behaviors. The longitudinal tensile strength of Epoxy-648 composite was 48% lower than Epoxy-634 composite's. The transverse tensile moduli and strengths of the unidirectional composites depend mainly on the characteristics of matrices and interfaces. The transverse tensile modulus of the Epoxy-634 composite was lower than the Epoxy-648 composite's. However, its tensile strength was 57% higher than Epoxy-648 composite's.

(2). In the unidirectional composites under compressive loads at fiber direction, the cracks in the matrices occurred first, then fibers were bended and finally composites were broken. Although the compressive strength of Epoxy-648 resin was higher than Epoxy-634's, the compressive strength of Epoxy-648 composite was 53% lower than Epoxy-634 composite's because its resistance to crack was lower than Epoxy-634's. Therefore, higher longitudinal compressive strength of composites result from good resistance and higher shear strength of the matrix resins.

(3). The shear modulus in plane of Epoxy-634 composite was less than Epoxy-648 composite's. However, its shear strength in plane was nearly as twice as the Epoxy-648 composite's, resulted from its higher resistance to crack.

The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of the unidirectional composites depend on matrix resistance to shear and bonding strength with fibers. The ILSS of Epoxy-634 composite was 57% higher than Epoxy-648 composite's.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The mechanical properties of the unidirectional composites were correlated closely with the matrix characteristics.
2. The tensile, compressive and shear moduli of unidirectional composites were increased with increasing of matrix moduli.
3. The longitudinal and trasverse tensile, longitudinal compressive and shear strengths were increased with increasing of matrix tensile strength and ultimate strains.
4. In the design of the composites, the matrices are selected according to the composite structures. The higher modulus matrix combined with higher modulus carbon fibers could be selected for the high stiffness structures. The higher tensile and shear strengths and large ultimate strain matrices combined with high strength carbon fibers could be selected for high stress structures:

Table 1. Mechanical Properties of Epoxy Matrces

Materials	648/BF ₃ .MEA	634/DDS
Tensile strength	33.3 Mpa	76.0 Mpa
Tensile modulus	3.0 Gpa	2.9 Gpa
Ultimate strain	1.24 %	2.66 %
Compressive strength	142.8 Mpa	118.0 Mpa
Compressive modulus	2.5 Gpa	2.3 Gpa

Table 2. Mechanical Properties of unidirectional Composites

Materials	T300/648	T300/634
Modulus (0 ⁰)	137 Gpa	133 Gpa
Modulus (90 ⁰)	9.1 Gpa	7.7 Gpa
Tensile strength (0 ⁰)	1051 Mpa	1559 Mpa
Tensile strength (90 ⁰)	33.5 Mpa	46.3 Mpa
Compressive strength (0 ⁰)	1015 Mpa	1556 Mpa
Shear Modulus in plane	5.3 Gpa	4.2 Gpa
Shear strength in plane	70.5 Mpa	139.5 Mpa
Interlaminar shear strength	49.9 Mpa	76.1 Mpa